

Non-viral siRNA delivery in RNA interference : Accomplishments, set-backs and future promises[†]

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Abstract : Ever since the disclosure of sequence-specific post-transcriptional gene silencing by RNA interference (RNAi) in cultured mammalian cells and in mammals, studies aimed at demonstrating therapeutic potential of small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) are being reported in mouse models, in non-human primates and most recently in humans. Despite significant progresses, clinical success of therapeutic RNA interference remains critically dependent on the availability of efficient siRNA delivery systems. Global efforts are being witnessed in developing both viral and non-viral vectors for *in vivo* delivery of therapeutic siRNAs. The present review is an attempt to update major achievements till date on design of efficient non-viral vectors for *in vivo* siRNA delivery and to highlight setbacks and unresolved issues and future prospects of this emerging field.

Keywords : *in vivo* siRNA delivery, non-viral vectors, setbacks, prospects.

Introduction

Complete sequencing of human genome has predicted the possible existence of ~25,000 genes in our body cells. Indubitably, for our proper functioning, expression of each of these genes needs to be under a tight spatio-temporal control mechanism. RNA interference (RNAi) is one such evolutionarily conserved unique spatio-temporal cellular surveillance mechanism with sequence-specific gene silencing capability. Briefly, mechanistic pathways in RNAi¹⁻³ involves three basic steps, namely, (i) ATP-dependent processing of endogenous or exogenous cytoplasmic long double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) precursors into ~21-23 nucleotide (nt) long double stranded short interfering RNAs (siRNAs) by dsRNA-specific RNase-III type endonucleases (Dicer); (ii) rearrangement of the resulting siRNA molecules into the multi-protein containing RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC) where the passenger strand (sense strand) of the siRNA gets degraded by the endonuclease Argonaute 2 (AGO2) of RISC and the guide strand (anti-sense strand) gets incorporated in RISC and (iii) sequence-specific hybridi-

zation of the guide strand with the target mRNA followed by multiple rounds of cleavage of the target mRNA mediated by antisense strand activated RISC (Fig. 1).

Ever since the disclosure of sequence-specific post-transcriptional gene silencing by RNA interference (RNAi) in cultured mammalian cells and in mammals^{3,4}, studies aimed at demonstrating therapeutic potential of small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) have been reported in mouse models⁵⁻⁹ as well as in non-human primates^{10,11} and most recently in humans¹². The distinguishing therapeutic advantages of using siRNAs over antisense therapy, the other widely exploited gene silencing protocol, are that siRNAs are significantly less susceptible than antisense oligonucleotides to assault by nucleases, thereby providing more prolonged therapeutic benefits. In addition, antisense therapies are less sequence-specific than RNAi-based therapeutic modalities and in consequence, the toxic side effects arising out of sequence-independent interactions often observed in antisense therapy are less of a problem for siRNAs¹³. However, primarily due to their highly

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Fig. 1. RNAi pathways.

polyanionic nature (~40 negative charge per single molecule of double stranded siRNA) and high molecular weight, siRNAs do not enter into cells spontaneously. Under systemic settings, successful delivery of intravenously administered siRNA in its active form to the desired body cells/tissues (where the target genes need to be silenced) is easier said than done. The numbers of physiological barriers to surmount are too many. siRNAs have to (i) reach their target body tissues/organs evading assault by systemic RNases and renal clearance mechanisms, (ii) enter target cells typically through endocytotic routes, (iii) cross the endosomal membranes to translocate themselves into the cell cytoplasm, and (iv) bind to and get loaded onto the RISC for effecting target mRNA cleavage by the AGO2 nucleases of RISC¹⁴. Clearly, rational design of efficient *in vivo* siRNA delivery systems needs to incorporate in its design elements mechanisms for enhancing the efficacies of all these steps. To this end, global efforts are being witnessed in developing both viral and non-viral vectors for *in vivo* delivery of therapeutic siRNAs. Viral vectors are usually highly efficient. However, their large scale productions are labor-intensive, costly and their uses are often associated with adverse

immunological responses originating from the residual virus structural elements. Contrastingly, the synthetic non-viral vectors for siRNA delivery are, in general, significantly less immunogenic than their viral counterparts and their robust manufactures are quite feasible. The present review is an attempt to update major achievements till date on design of efficient non-viral vectors for *in vivo* siRNA delivery and to highlight set backs and unresolved issues, future prospects of this emerging field.

Contemporary non-viral siRNA delivery vectors

The existing arsenal of non-viral *in vivo* siRNA delivery reagents can be broadly classified and discussed under the following categories.

Lipid based siRNA systems :

Nanometric lipid based (mostly cationic liposomes, aggregates of bilayers of cationic lipids with an watery interior) systems are being widely used by numerous research groups, biotechnology and pharmaceutical companies across the globe for *in vivo* delivery of siRNAs. Since cationic liposomes have been successfully used in the past for delivering plasmid DNA encoded genes in non-viral gene therapy of myriads of infectious diseases

and cancer¹⁵⁻¹⁷, they have been the default non-viral vector of choice for *in vivo* delivery of siRNAs. Many cationic lipid-based formulations are currently under pre-clinical and clinical evaluation. The first non-human primate study using lipid-based siRNA delivery system was carried out using stable nucleic acid lipid particles (SNALPs, Fig. 2) containing siRNAs entrapped inside the aqueous com-

Fig. 2. Cartoon for SNALPs.

partment of a liposome prepared from a cationic lipid, a fusion-regulating and circulation-stabilizing polyethylene glycol-conjugated lipid (PEG-lipid) and a neutral lipid¹⁸. SNALP-entrapped siRNA nanoparticles exhibit longer half-life in plasma and liver when compared to half-lives of siRNA encapsulated within the aqueous compartments of conventional liposomes. Leveraging on the liver-targeting characteristics of SNALPs, Alnylam Pharmaceuticals (Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA) and Tekmira Pharmaceuticals (Burnaby, British Columbia, Canada) successfully developed siRNA therapeutics for liver diseases using APOBsiRNA^{19,20} and KSPsiRNA²¹. Scientists at Silence Therapeutics (London, UK) succeeded in knocking down the expression of PKN3 gene in tumor vascular endothelium by using liposomally packaged siRNA against PKN3 gene-encoding protein kinase N3 and subsequently have demonstrated inhibition of lung metastasis in animal tumor models^{22,23}. This product has been approved for human clinical trial²⁴. Recently, using a syngeneic C57BL/6J mice tumor model, we have shown that intraperitoneal administration of a 19 bp synthetic CDC20 siRNA encap-

sulated within liposomes of a guanidinylated cationic amphiphile with two hydrophobic stearyl tails (Fig. 3) inhibits B16F10 solid tumor growth. Furthermore, using an established spontaneous mouse lung metastasis, we showed that intravenous administration of 19 bp CDC20 siRNA encapsulated within such liposomes inhibits B16F10 melanoma growth on lung²⁵.

Fig. 3. (a) Structures of the guanidinylated cationic amphiphiles used for *in vitro* and systemic delivery of CDC20 siRNA; (b) sequence of mouse CDC20 siRNA.

Lipidoids, a recently developed lipid-like less cytotoxic nano-metric non-viral delivery systems prepared by combinatorial synthetic strategies (Fig. 4), are finding increasing applications as vectors for siRNAs in therapeutic RNA interference²⁶. Simple one- or two-steps synthetic schemes (Fig. 4) provided easy access to large li-

Fig. 4. (a) Synthesis of lipidoids by the conjugate addition of amine to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds. (b) Schematic synthesis of lipidoids by the conjugate addition of amine to epoxides. (c) Structure of 2,2-dilinoleyl-4-dimethyl-aminoethyl-[1,3]-dioxolane (DLin-KC2-DMA).

braries of lipidoids (~1200 molecules) through conjugate addition of different amines to structurally well de-

finer various α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds²⁶. Studies aimed at evaluating therapeutic potentials of lipidoids showed that lipidoid-formulated CLDN3 siRNA holds potential for combating ovarian cancer²⁷. Like SNALPs, lipidoid-formulated siRNAs get selectively accumulated in mouse liver^{28,29}. A distinct systemic advantage of lipidoid-formulated siRNAs over conventional liposome-entrapped siRNAs is that only a tiny fraction of the injected lipidoid-formulated siRNA does is required to achieve the same level of knockdown efficiencies²⁸.

Non-lipid based siRNA delivery systems :

Several non-viral siRNA delivery systems based on elegant use of non-lipid molecules are emerging as promising class of non-viral siRNA delivery systems. Based on their different chemical constituents, these emerging non-viral siRNA vectors are discussed below under the following sub-classes :

Cyclodextrin-based siRNA delivery system :

Davis and co-workers recently developed a cyclodextrin-based nanometric system consisting of a polycationic linear cyclodextrin polymer (CDP) as the building block with hydrophilic PEG-molecules linked to them via hydrophobic adamantane molecule (Fig. 5). Aimed at targeting such CDP-based siRNA delivery systems selectively to tumor cells, human transferrin ligands were covalently conjugated to some of the PEG molecules (transferrin receptors are found to be overexpressed on

Fig. 5. Cartoon for transferrin (TF) receptor targeting CDP-siRNA nanoparticles. The polyethylene glycol (PEG) molecules are covalently linked with adamantane (AD) which in turn form inclusion complexes with surface cyclodextrins. The surface of the CDP-siRNA nanoparticles are decorated with PEG for steric stabilization and PEG-TF for targeting to transferrin receptors.

the surface of many cancer cells). The resulting CDP-conjugates (Fig. 5) efficiently delivered siRNA against the M2 subunit of ribonucleotide reductase in non-human primates³⁰ and most importantly in humans¹².

Chemical conjugates of siRNAs :

Studies aimed at enhancing cellular uptake of siRNAs and protecting siRNAs from assault by systemic RNases through chemical conjugation of siRNAs with appropriate cell penetrating peptides (CPP), small drug molecules, lipids, aptamers or polymers have been reported. For instance, in a recent study, the ds-GFPsiRNA was chemically conjugated with a phosphothioethanol via a reducible disulfide linker and the resulting siRNA-S-S-PE conjugate (Fig. 6a) was incorporated in a nanometric PEG-PE micelles. The PEG-PE micelle associated GFPsiRNA-S-S-PE exhibited stability against nucleases and could down regulate the GFP production in GFP-C166 endothelial cells 50 times more effectively than free unconjugated GFPsiRNA with no cellular cytotoxicity³¹. A siRNA with chemically modified thiophosphate backbone was conjugated to a lipophilic cholesterol unit at the 3'-end of its sense strand. The resulting lipophilic conjugate of the backbone modified siRNA (Fig. 6b) upon intravenous administration degraded apolipoprotein B mRNA by ~60% in the liver. Importantly, no adverse immune response or off-target effects were observed in mice even at a high dose of 50 mg/kg³². More recently, it has been demonstrated that the cholesterol-siRNA conjugate enters hepatocytes in complexation with lipoproteins³³. Park *et al.* conjugated siRNA to circulation stabilizing PEG via a reducible disulfide bond and then complexed the siRNA-S-S-PEG conjugate with cationic polymers or peptides as a core condensing agent³⁴⁻⁴⁰. The resulting colloidal nanoparticles were found to be effective for local as well as systemic treatments of tumor in animal models³⁴⁻⁴⁰.

Wolff and co-workers succeeded in developing a non-toxic and well tolerated vehicle, which they named "siRNA Dynamic Polyconjugates" for both *in vitro* and *in vivo* delivery of siRNAs to hepatocytes⁴¹. The key features of this siRNA dynamic polyconjugates include a membrane-active polymer, the ability to reversibly mask the activity of this polymer until it reaches the acidic endosomal compartments in the cell cytoplasm and the ability to target the conjugated siRNA to hepatocytes *in vivo* upon intra-

Fig. 6. Chemical structures of siRNA-S-S-PE (a) and lipophile-siRNA conjugates (b).

venous administration in mice. Using such siRNA dynamic polyconjugates, they demonstrated effective knock-down of two endogenous genes in mouse liver namely, apolipoprotein B (apoB) and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (ppara).

Cationic polymer mediated siRNA delivery :

High transfection efficiencies of linear cationic polyethyleneimine and control release characteristics of the solid lipid particles have been elegantly exploited recently

in developing a solid lipid-PEI hybrid nano-vector for extended, targeted and safer siRNA therapy of prostate cancer⁴². Nanoparticles formed by interactions between siRNAs and chitosan, the naturally occurring non-inflammatory, non-toxic and biodegradable cationic polysaccharide (Fig. 7), have been used to mediate 90% reduced expression of BCR/ABL-1 leukemia fusion protein⁴³. Effective mucosal RNA interference was demonstrated in bronchiole epithelial cells of transgenic EGFP mice after

Fig. 7. Chemical structure of chitosan.

nasal administration of chitosan/siRNA nanoparticles⁴³. More recently, Mittnacht *et al.* reported on the use of chitosan/siRNA nanoparticles to facilitate their effective immobilization on neuronal microimplants toward enabling neurite outgrowth in the presence of inhibitory myelin⁴⁴. Hue *et al.* demonstrated effective tumor-targeting ability of glycol chitosan-PEI nanoparticles in a mouse tumor model⁴⁵.

Cell-penetrating peptide-mediated siRNA delivery :

Cell-penetrating peptides (CPPs), including HIV-1 TAT protein, polyarginine (R4-R16), etc. have been shown to be efficient in delivering siRNAs both into cultured animal cells and *in vivo*⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹. The overall positive charges of the CPP-siRNA complexes help their membrane translocation⁵⁰. Electrostatic complexes of siRNA and cell-penetrating MPG-peptide (GALFLGFLGAAGSTMGAWSQPKKKRKV-cysteamide) were successfully used by Simeoni *et al.* for introducing siRNAs into cells⁵¹. More recently, Crombez *et al.* succeeded in elegantly exploiting a secondary amphipathic peptide CADY (GLWRALWRLRLSLWRLWRA-cysteamide), a 20 amino acids cell-penetrating peptide with aromatic tryptophan and 5

positively charged arginine residues, for enhancing cellular uptake efficiencies of siRNAs in difficult-to-transfect cells⁵². CADY adopts a helical conformation within the cell membranes, thereby exposing the charged residues on one side and the Trp groups that favor cellular uptake on the other side⁵². Subsequently, by applications of molecular modeling, spectroscopy and membrane interactions, they showed that CADY-siRNA complexes bind with the membrane phospholipids mainly through electrostatic interactions. They proposed that CADY cellular membrane interactions were driven by its structural polymorphism, which improved stabilization of both electrostatic and hydrophobic contacts with cell surface proteoglycans and phospholipids⁵³. The efficiency of siRNA-CPP complexes in inducing RNAi is often restricted by their entrapment in endosome-lysosome compartments after endocytotic cell internalization. Stated differently, developing CPPs that promote rapid endosomal escape is a prerequisite for effective induction of RNAi. To this end, Andaloussi *et al.* recently developed PepFect 6 (PF6), a novel class of CPP comprising of a previously reported stearyl-TP10 peptide having covalently grafted pH titratable trifluoromethylquinoline moieties (Fig. 8) for facilitating endosomal release⁵⁴. In this work, they demonstrated that stable PF6/siRNA nanoparticles enter cells and get rapidly released from endosomal compartments, thereby inducing robust RNAi responses in various cell types including primary cells with minimal associated transcriptomic or proteomic changes. Most importantly, these siRNA-PF6 particles showed strong RNAi response in different organs following systemic delivery in mice without any associated toxicity⁵⁴.

Fig. 8. Chemical structures of the various components of PF6 : TP10 backbone (1), succinylated trifluoroquinoline-based derivative (2), PepFect3 (3), trifluoroquinoline-based derivative conjugated to succinylated Lys7 of TP10 (4), PepFect5 (5) and PepFect6 (6).

Inorganic nanoparticles-mediated siRNA delivery :

Efforts are now being directed on developing efficient nanometric siRNA delivery reagents through conjugation of inorganic nanoparticles in general and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) in particular. Distinguishing advantages in using AuNPs for delivering siRNAs into body cells include their biocompatibility, easy synthesis, mono-dispersity and the straightforward functionalization procedures. AuNP-siRNA conjugates are emerging as a highly promising class of non-viral siRNA vectors. For instance, Giljohann *et al.* reported on the development of first polyvalent RNA-AuNP conjugates through use of ethylene glycol spacer and an alkylthiol group which could effectively regulate expression of genes⁵⁵. Lee *et al.* designed a novel Au-NP based efficient siRNA delivery systems in which the AuNPs were modified with PEG and the siRNA was conjugated to the PEG-modified AuNPs via biodegradable disulfide linkers with coatings of poly(β -amino ester)s being finally applied on the surface of resulting nanoparticles⁵⁶.

Set-backs, challenges and future prospects

Despite the above-mentioned progresses, many unresolved mechanistic and technical issues are impeding the clinical success of non-viral siRNA therapeutics. The poor efficiency of non-viral siRNA delivery systems is a major retarding factor. The cellular uptake mechanisms of siRNA, their intracellular transport and their endosomal release mechanisms are, at the best, poorly understood. Efforts to this end have just begun. Very recently, Gilleron *et al.* monitored the uptake of lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) loaded with traceable siRNAs in different cell types *in vitro* and in mouse liver by quantitative fluorescence imaging and electron microscopy⁵⁷. In this work, they have shown that LNPs enter cells using both clathrin-mediated endocytosis as well as through macropinocytosis. By electron microscopic estimation of colloidal-Au particles conjugated siRNAs, they observed that escape of siRNA from endosome to cell cytoplasm occurs with very low frequency (1–2%) and occurs only when the LNPs are located in specific compartment sharing early and late endosomal traits⁵⁷. Clearly, inclusion of strong membrane disrupting ingredients need to be used in future toward ensuring enhanced endosomal release of siRNAs. However, caution needs to be exercised in using CPPs con-

taining too many amino acid residues with very high pKa (such as polyarginines) since such amino acid residues in CPPs will always remain protonated and will, therefore, remain closely bound with siRNAs, thereby inhibiting cytoplasmic release of siRNAs from endosome. In another very recent elegant study aimed at understanding the interactions between LNP-siRNA complexes and cells, Sahay *et al.* examined cellular uptake of siRNA delivered by LNPs using various cellular trafficking probes in combination with high-throughput confocal microscopy⁵⁸. They induced defined perturbations of cellular pathways and applied system biology approaches to understand protein-protein and protein-small molecules interactions. Interestingly, they showed that multiple cell signaling effectors are required for initial cellular entry of the LNP-siRNA complexes through macropinocytosis including proton pumps, mTOR and cathepsins. Most importantly, they showed that siRNA delivery is remarkably reduced as ~70% of the internalized siRNAs undergoes exocytosis through egress of LNPs from late endosome-lysosome compartments⁵⁸. These findings are highly consistent with the supposition that LNP-mediated siRNA delivery efficiencies might be improved in future by designing novel siRNA delivery formulations that can evade cellular recycling pathways.

On the systemic issues, the reticulo-endothelial organs such as the liver and spleen are densely populated by specialized cells of immune cells such as Kupffer cells in liver and the specialized macrophages which accumulate in the splenic white pulp. Thus, these organs function as natural filters protecting our bodies from foreign invaders such as pathogenic microorganisms and macromolecules. Despite the protecting stealth effects exhibited by the pegylated siRNA vectors (which minimizes uptake of delivery systems by body's reticulo-endothelial systems, RES), the nano-vectors are never completely protected. This is why a major fraction of systemically administered siRNA-nanoparticles get accumulated in RES where siRNAs are usually degraded. Future design of siRNA delivery systems needs to address on how to evade RES while in circulation.

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